

The Effects of Implementing ICT in Teaching and Learning English

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Abstract: Technology has become an important aspect in our lives since it is used nowadays in different ways for different purposes. The development of technology has helped a lot in the teaching process. During the last two decades, the educational systems all over the world are seeking for suitable methods to apply technology in teaching and learning English to reach the goals of effective teaching. Therefore, educators have been searching for the best way to employ technology in education. Information and Communication Technology (ICT) has become a real topic of interest in the field of language teaching. It can be used by the learner and the instructor in the process of language learning and teaching. Using ICT in teaching can be a tool to help the instructor facilitate language learning. Therefore, the purpose of this study is to focus on the benefits of using ICT in English teaching and learning and to find out the challenges that may face the learner and the instructor of English language when using ICT in teaching and learning English

Keywords: Technology – ICT (Information Communication Technology) – Teaching and Learning English.

1. INTRODUCTION

Technology has become an integrated part in all fields of our life. It is used a lot by different people everywhere and every time. It has revolutionized the way we live, interact with each other and the way we work.

Today, the technological-integrated approaches are used widely as learning tools and as a pedagogical factor in education. They are used to facilitate the learning process and to develop the educational policies. The economic, political, business and social challenges facing the world today demand ICT media and literacy skills as the basic skills that should be required by the students (Pratama, 2015). The rapid development in the way we live leads to the need of changing the way we teach and learn. In another words, education is a dynamic phenomenon that needs to align with the current trends in society, in order to address the conflicts of multiple technologies (Tawil, 2018). Nowadays, technology is used widely in most of the educational administrations in order to improve the educational system.

In this computerized environment, learners and instructors are obliged to deal with technology in the term of learning or teaching. It becomes essential to develop the students' learning skills in dealing with technology.

During the last decade, it has been generally noticeable the strong relation between people specifically teenagers and technology. People spend most of their time on the internet using different types of devices for different purposes. Today web sites are widely used by various people in different fields since, accessing the internet now means accessing universal education.

Generally, the aim of using ICT in education is to improve the teaching and learning process. Nowadays, the new generation either instructors or learners have a wide experience in using technology. They are engaged with different types of devices in all aspects of their lives; Therefore, it will be a great benefit to manipulate their interest and positive attitudes towards using technological tools in the teaching and learning process. Using technology helps teachers to develop classroom activities and the learning process.

Teaching English by using the traditional teaching methods depended on in-class lectures and on drilling some activities by the learners. But, recently, with the new era of using technology in all the aspects of our life, many academic language institutions have started to implement ICT in the educational syllabuses. It becomes one of the priorities of the educational administrations

The effectiveness of ICT depends mainly on the teachers' motivation and the way it is used. Instructors should choose the suitable technological tool for each method of teaching. Using ICT technology in education requires using smart boards, smartphones, computers and the Internet.

Using technology platforms in teaching helps a lot in improving the teaching environment. The instructor's role will be expanded from just a teacher to an organizer, a facilitator and prompter. This enables the learners to participate in the learning process and be responsible for their own learning while having all the support from their teacher. This will lead instructors to deal with different educational factors such as learners' individual differences, the learners' different personal characteristics and with the variety of learning styles. Technology provides learners the chance to work individually and interact with others online. This will help to develop learner's autonomy. Also, it helps instructors to discover his learners' skills, So, teaching English with the help on online websites will help a lot in developing the learners' skills in listening, speaking, reading and writing.

Technological tools can be used to support the teaching methods by providing different activities that will help in achieving the goals of teaching. Therefore, using technology in teaching will lead to a successful learning process.

The word "Technology" has been defined by many resources. Oxford Dictionary had provided three definitions for it. One of them, which applies to this study, "Machinery and equipment developed from the application of scientific knowledge". Wikipedia has defined the word "Technology" as "The sum of techniques, skills, methods and processes used in the production of goods or services or in the accomplishment of objectives, such as scientific investigations. Regarding the aspect of teaching, Wikipedia has defined "Educational Technology" as the combined use of computer hardware, software and educational theory and practice to facilitate learning". The Association for educational Communication and Technology (AECT) defined "Educational Technology as "The study and ethical practice of facilitating learning and improving performance by creating, using and managing appropriate technological process and resources". Those definitions clarify the importance of using technology in the educational environment.

ICT (Information, Communication, and Technology) is a form of using technology which includes using tools like, audio-visual aids in addition to digital tools such as, computers and the internet that help a lot in developing the educational process.

Instructors consider ICT as a great educational resource of information and a good mean for delivering classroom information. Moreover, it provides them with valuable tools to communicate with their learners. For learners, ICT provides them the opportunities to communicate more effectively and to develop literacy skills including skills in critical literacy. It is a valuable tool that facilitates comprehending, researching, and creativity. Modern ICT such as the internet, computers, laptops smartphones and others in teaching English are used widely nowadays to facilitate applying new methods and techniques in teaching that lead to the achievement of the desired goals of teaching. When integrating ICT in teaching foreign language, learners will be able to learn through practicing and entertaining.

ICT has helped to develop education from instructor - centered as in the traditional methods to learner - centered. It has shifted the instructor's role from being a source of information to being a guide to search for information. Therefore, learners will take more responsibility for their own learning and, also, it will stimulate learners' initiatives and provides more effective environments for English teaching. Moreover, it will improve the learners' ability to listen and speak and then, improve their communication skills. This will help them increase self-confidence and self-esteem. Therefore, using ICT tools in learning English ensures a continuous learning process that starts from the classroom and goes on either at home or anywhere else. In the classroom, using of ICT tools such as in smartboards or computers, and using tools like the internet or smart phones outside the classroom, helps learner to engage with their teachers constantly.

By implementing ICT tools that includes using the Internet, technological devices such as computers, laptops, smartphones...etc, learners can surf through the Internet to search for the information needed. The use of those devices helps to turn dull subjects into interactive and fun activities. This will make the learning process more interesting, motivating, stimulating and meaningful for the learners. Also, using ICT in learning English helps learners to find out the

information easily and to learn at their own pace. Moreover, it provides great opportunities for communications and collaboration between learners among different countries. They can interact and share what they have learnt with learners in other classrooms in other countries. This will be very motivating for them to learn the language.

While using ICT in teaching English, instructors can use the internet to surf through countless educational activities and materials. Therefore, instructors can use the internet to prepare their lessons and to search for topics that will help in facilitating their lessons and then choosing the suitable activities and technological tools to provide an effective learning environment. Using ICT helps instructors to find easier ways to create instructional materials. It helps them to prepare and store their own teaching materials. Also, it provides them with different topics, exercises and quizzes that will save their time an effort. Using multimedia in teaching English will help instructors to present their lessons in a more attractive and interesting way as multimedia combines sound, images, and text. The use of audio/ visual methods in teaching English helps a lot in presenting information easily and this will increase the learners' interest and motivation in studying because using multimedia in teaching English helps to bring real-life situations into the teaching process. And this will satisfy both the visual and auditory senses of the learners. The internet provides wide selections of educational images, videos and audios designed either for instructors and learners.

Integrating ICT in teaching English is crucial, because using this technology ensures continuous learning that is happening inside and outside the educational institution. Teaching through technology helps instructors to present lessons by using various materials such as, educational videos, World Wide Web (www), stimulations and brainstorming that will achieve effective learning process.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Due to the new era of ICT (Information Communication Technology) revolution and its extensive integration into education, many studies investigated the influence of technological tools and approaches in teaching and learning English.

Many studies have researched the effects of using technology in teaching English language. Susan & Oluwatoyin, (2013) have discussed the challenges of computer technology in the teaching and learning of spoken English in Tertiary Institution in Nigeria. Depending on the teachers and learners' responses, it was revealed that using technology in teaching English may face some challenges such as: the non- availability of computer equipment, poor learning environment with high number of learners, inadequate computer knowledge and skills, and maintenance of computer equipment. In his study about the effect of using computer technology on English language teachers' performance,

Saeed, (2015) found that many teachers of English have positive attitudes towards teaching English through computers.

The researcher has revealed some issues regarding using computer in teaching English such as: lack of access to computers, teachers' lack of computer knowledge and lack of computer training. In another study about teaching and learning with technology and the effectiveness of ICT integration in schools, Ghavifekr and Rosdy (2015) have applied a survey questionnaire for teachers to analyse their perceptions on the effectiveness of integrating ICT in teaching and learning. The results showed that both teachers and learners get the most benefits from implementing ICT in the learning process. The researchers mentioned some elements that affect the quality of learning. They noted that teachers' well-preparation and the developed training programs have great impacts on the learning process.

Amina & Salim (2015) have focused on the use of educational technology in EFL teaching and learning. They have concluded that both teachers and learners have positive attitudes towards using technology in the teaching and learning process. also, it was mentioned that using educational technology needs money to be provided in the right way. Moreover, using educational technology needs a good technological knowledge either by teachers or learners. They found that using computers in the classroom can waste the time.

Çakici, (2016) has investigated the use of ICT in teaching English as a foreign language. The researcher concluded that implementing ICT in EFL enhances the learners' skills in solving problems, helps learners to use higher order skills, improves the skills of critical thinking and information processing. It also encourages autonomous and collaborative learning. The researcher emphasized that integrating ICT in teaching foreign languages should be implied as effective and valuable teaching tool.

In their study about the use of ICT in English language teaching and learning, Jayanthi & Kumar (2016) have concluded that the use of ICTs in language teaching has supported the richness and quality of education both on and off campus. It was mentioned how multimedia technologies such as the videodiscs, CD-ROMs, DVDs and Power Point projects can be applied in teaching different aspects of English language such as literature, writing, vocabulary development and grammar.

Gunuc & Babacan (2017) have searched the importance of ICT tools in teaching – learning process of basic English language skills. They have concluded that the process of technology integration in English teaching and learning needs to be carried out consciously and in a planned way in order to make significant contributions to the use of technology which is an essential task for teachers.

Benefits of Implementing ICT in Teaching and Learning English

There are undeniable benefits of using technology in teaching English. Many researchers have found that technology-based teaching contributes greatly to the quality of teaching. Using technology in teaching has shown a lot of positive effects in teaching English. It provides great opportunities for language usage that will help in the learning process. ICT gives learners different opportunities to practice language skills in and out the classroom. Learners can follow up with their lessons and instructors at any time outside their class. Instructors can interact with their learners at any time by using the e-mail for example, and this will ensure a continuous learning.

ICTs provide many opportunities for the learners to practice English in and out the classroom. Using the technological tools such as, internet, smart phones, smart boards, videos etc in teaching English provides teachers with a variety of pedagogical methods and at the same time, helps learners to improve their level in the target language. This will lead to an interactive and flexible teaching environment.

Instructors can benefit from the availability of online tests that examine the four types of language skills: Listening, Speaking, Reading and writing. There are several computer-assisted packages that provide different types of tests with different types of questions. Instructors will find it very easy to prepare tests and to mark them online as there are many applications that provide auto-correction feature, and this will save a lot of time and effort for the teacher. Also, most of the learners find it easier to deal with computers in answering tests than writing on papers as computers provide some features like spelling correction and grammar correction. Another advantage of online tests is that they provide learners with immediate results of their answers.

The Effects of Implementing ICT on English Language Skills

The English language integrates four main skills: listening, speaking, reading and writing. The skills of listening and reading are considered input skills and sometimes they are called "receptive skills". While, speaking and writing are considered output skills and sometimes they are called "productive skills". In this section, the effects of implementing ICT in teaching and learning English on the four language skills will be discussed.

1. The Role of ICT in Improving the Listening Skill

One of the basic skills in learning English is listening. It is a receptive skill that combines comprehending the accent of the speaker, the pronunciations of words, the intonation, the meaning of the used words and situation where the speaking occurs.

Multimedia technologies such as audio, video and animation are becoming commonplace and becoming a potential tool for listening (Gunuc & Babacan, 2017). So, it was proved that using ICT tools in teaching English enhances learners' listening skills and develops learners' self-confidence in terms of listening.

With the use of tools such as radio, audiotapes, podcasts, tape recorders, IPODs and videos in English teaching and learning, learners can comprehend intonation and learn the pronunciation of words and experience different accents (Nomass 2013).

In his study about the impact of technology in teaching English as a second language, Diliprao (2016) has mentioned several ways to use technological tools to improve listening skills by using technology:

1) Using computers: It provides learners with visual and voice materials that can improve their listening skill.

- 2) Broadcasting: Satellite TV channels are useful for practicing with audio and video media.
- 3) Using C.D. players: C.D. players are used to play audio CD-ROMs. Lectures and listening examinations can be saved CDs for listening.
- 4) Using tape recorders

2. The Role of ICT on Improving the Speaking skill

Speaking is the productive skill in the oral mode. It is considered a complicated skill. It is more than just pronouncing words. The speaking skill is the ultimate goal for language learners. Through different studies, it was proved that this skill can be developed by using ICT tools. In his study about teaching of communication skills using multimedia and language laboratory, Bachate (2016) has proved that language laboratories have positive effects on learners' communication and speaking skills.

In their study about the effects of storytelling to facilitate EFL speaking using Web-based multimedia system, Hwang et al., (2016) found that the technique of web-based storytelling motivates the learners and encourages them to practice speaking and promotes their creativity and imagination. Sun et al., (2017) mentioned that social networking systems have developed ESL learners' speaking skills.

Diliprao (2016) has mentioned ways to use technological tools to improve the skill of Speaking:

- 1) Internet Voice chatting: Chatting is a way of voice communication between the speaker and the listener through the internet.
- 2) Speech synthesis programs: These are artificial intelligence computer programs which can be used to improve the speaking capability.

3. The Role ICT in Improving the Reading Skill

Reading is considered one of the four basic skills in learning English. It is a productive skill that has many benefits such as, mental stimulation, stress reduction, knowledge increase, vocabulary expansion, entertainment, and improvement in one's analytical thinking skills among others (Maduabuchi, 2016). Reading is a skill that helps in building vocabulary that leads to a better listening comprehension skill. ICT can be used to teach the reading skill. There are many ICT tools used to teach reading. For example, learners can improve their reading skills with tools such as browsing the Internet, using multimedia software, using electronic dictionaries and gloss, reading newspapers/books on the internet, and using reading-based computer programs (Nomass 2013). Moreover, using the internet to read magazines, newspapers, encyclopaedias may contribute a lot in the development of the learners' reading skills. There are different educational websites that teach reading skills and at the same time help a lot in learning vocabulary.

Diliprao (2016) has mentioned ways to use technological tools to improve the skill of reading:

- 1) Computer Reading Based Programs: These programs help to develop learners' vocabulary, oral fluency, and comprehension.
- 2) Multimedia Software: These programs combine text, animation, videos graphics and sounds which motivate learners to improve their vocabulary and reading skills.
- 3) Electronic dictionaries: These dictionaries provide various functions that are not found in book dictionaries. They are easy to use and considered quick tools for acquiring vocabulary.

4. The Role of ICT in Improving the Writing Skill

Writing is considered a productive skill. This skill requires performing some tasks like planning, organizing, using the suitable structure, grammar and vocabulary and generating ideas. It was proved through different studies that technology helped a lot in developing the learners' writing skills.

Nowadays practicing writing by using technological devices such as computers, laptops, iPads, and iPhones is a way of communicating with each other. Emails have replaced the paper letters. Many computer programs provide easy-typing process since they provide the facilities of correcting spelling, grammar and the style of writing. That what makes learning writing is much easier.

Writing could be practiced by using different technological tools such as; writing e-mails, writing through social networks and internet-text chatting. By using those tools, learners could interact with their peers through chatting which may help in developing their writing skills.

Diliprao (2016) has mentioned ways to use technological tools to improve the skill of writing:

- 1) Using of computers: Most learners find it challenging to write paragraphs or essays in a foreign language. Using computers will help them a lot in writing and improving sentence structure and grammar.
- 2) Writing e-mails: writing electronic mails is a good way for writing messages through the internet.

Negative Aspects of Implementing ICT in Teaching and Learning English

Using ICT in teaching and learning English may have negative aspects either on learners or on the methods of teaching.

In a study about the use of ICT in teaching writing skills, Yunus et al (2013) have found that using ICT in teaching the writing skills for ESL could have some disadvantages. Teachers may face difficulties in controlling the class while using technological tools. Learners tend to use abbreviations in their writing. Also, the study showed that most teachers are not quailed enough to prepare class activities or to manage class and learners' problems.

The internet provides a variety of websites and applications for playing games and puzzles that may distract the learners' attention. Learners tend not to participate in the class because of the distraction while playing online games. This will make it difficult for the teachers to control and manage the class.

Many studies have approved that using ICT in teaching and learning English may waste the learners' time. The learner may be distracted by other entertaining apps instead of using the laptop or the smart phone in the learning activities.

As for instructors, using ICT in teaching may waste the instructors' time since each instructor needs to prepare material that suit the use of technology in the class. Abunowara (2016) mentioned some disadvantages of using technology in the EFL classroom. He pointed out that using ICT in teaching may waste time and require great efforts to search for authentic materials since instructors a long time in learning constantly, choosing suitable software programs and looking for ways to use technology effectively. In addition, instructors need to look for the best way to merge the new syllabus and the tools with the already used syllabus. This method takes a lot of time and effort from the instructors.

Çakici (2016) has mentioned some issues that may face the implementation of ICT language classroom. The researcher has concluded some issues like, weakness in the management of the class, the lack of qualified instructors, selecting technological tool that suit the course content, aims, and learners' abilities, the high cost of new devices, and searching for reliable activities that fulfil the teaching goals.

Generally, the implementation of ICT in teaching and learning English needs some training either for learners or instructors since this implementation require dealing with technological tools. Using technology in education may have negative aspects in case of teacher ineffective control. It may lead to a loss of time and classroom control. ICT is not suitable for all learners in all situations and for all purposes and may require some considerable learner training for effective use (Livingstone, 2012).

3. RECOMMENDATIONS

Implementing ICT in teaching and learning English is a very useful method that may have great effects on the learning process. Therefore, to get the ultimate benefit of this implementation, educational institutions should prepare special courses for teachers and students about how to use the technological tools effectively in teaching and learning. Using technology needs continuous training for teachers and learners to follow the technical development. They need to acquire sufficient ICT skills to be able to implement technology in teaching and learning English. They also need to have high self-confident to use it in the classroom. Moreover, instructors should provide their learners with interactive activities that suit their needs and encourage them to use technology in developing the language skills. The technological tools that could be used as learning tools should be part of the learning activities.

As a result, acquiring technological skills becomes one of the basic requirements in institutions around the world today. Educators and learners need to coop with this revolution by developing their skills in using technology.

Educational institutions should focus more on developing language skills of the educators and learners as well to reach high standards of educational levels. With the development of technology in the 21st century, teachers and learners are facing great challenges to develop their teaching and learning skills in a way that leads to the improvement of the educational system.

4. CONCLUSION

This study underscores the benefits and the challenges of implementing ICT in teaching and learning English. It was found that using ICT in teaching has great educational benefits over the obstacles. Using ICT will lead to positive outcomes especially when following up an elaborated plan on how to set up using technology in teaching.

Implementing educational technology and communication into teaching and learning English has proved that it enhances the learners' skills in problem solving, gives the opportunity to improve critical thinking. Instructors should know their learners' socio-culture, their qualifications, their competence in technology, their preferable technological tools, their attitude towards technology and their economic levels. Technological tools like, computers, smart phones, smart boards, the internet and websites proved to be affective in learning process and help achieve the general aims of the teaching process. As a sequence, using ICT effectively in education, that includes using various developed educational tools, will prompt and enrich the quality of education.

It is necessary for both instructors and learners to have basic technological knowledge in order to achieve effective language education. Therefore, educational managements should prepare training courses for both instructors and learners to develop their competencies in using technology since using technological devices by the learners to learn English would help prepare them for the digital future.

In conclusion, integrating ICT in teaching and learning English needs to be planned effectively to ensure the achievement of high standard and developed process of teaching and learning English.

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